

THE ARTLESS PIRENNIAN*

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A product of about five years' research on a fabulous fellowship, the originality of André Wink's book is truly radical—from the roots. Wink brushes aside the whole gamut of writings on early medieval India in the current historiography. He is hard on the "feudalism studies" led by R.S. Sharma and shows equal contempt for those who have been critical of the framework of feudalism (despite a sop to them on p. 223):

These authors echo R.S. Sharma, whose *Indian Feudalism* has misguided *virtually all* historians of the period, not only because it is entirely written from the a priori assumption of the 'dark age', doggedly searching for point by point parallels with Europe, but also, more accidentally, *because there has never been anything to challenge it* (pp. 220-21) (emphases added).

But the Gibbon and Pirenne theses still hold India in a desperate double clutch: here the barbarian invasions and the rise of Islam *compounded* are responsible for the onset of the Middle Ages and for 'feudalism'. *The usefulness of this periodization, of the entire analogy with Europe, has never been seriously questioned* (p. 224) (second emphasis added).

What needs to be done? Simple: "To see what goes on we merely have to take our sources seriously" (p. 231).

Indeed, André Wink offers us a set of startling conclusions: European historians do not just reject Pirenne's thesis that Islam in its early centuries dried up trade in the Mediterranean but speak of the economic hegemony of Islam over Europe in the Early Middle Ages. This Pirennian view must be rejected for early medieval India as well. In fact, from the seventh to the eleventh century the Indian economy, just like the contemporary European one, was subservient to the dominant world economy of the Muslim Middle East. By organizing diasporas along the Indian coast, the "Muslim economy" took care of the "production outlets" of the various regional economies of India. The expansion of local production and internal trade, "the successful expansion of regional economies" providing the "material impetus" for the formation of regional polities, the regional polities in turn promoting brāhmanical resurgence—all these processes are "unthinkable" without this role of Islam. While the regional economies through their contact with the "Muslim economy" enabled regional polities to assert their autonomy, the special favour bestowed by this economy on the Rāṣṭrakūṭas enabled them to exercise "paramourty" over the rest of India for about two hundred years. Earlier, it was external help from the Chinese that enabled first the Kashmir king Lalitāditya and then the Pāla king Dharmapāla (who received Kashmiri help as well) to exercise this "paramourty". After the Rāṣṭrakūṭas this "overlordship" was exercised by the Cōlas during the eleventh and twelfth centuries, thanks again to the importance of their external trade (pp. 34-36, 225, 230).

* Based on André Wink, *Al-Hind: The Making of the Indo-Islamic World*, Vol. I, *Early Medieval India and the Expansion of Islam* (E.J. Brill, Leiden; Oxford University Press, Delhi, 1990). Pp. viii + 396. Rs 250.00.

If such conclusions could be drawn from the sources, the historians have certainly not taken the sources seriously so far, or we are witnessing a breath-taking, paradigmatic change in our discipline. It is evident that Wink's is an attempt to colonize the early medieval Indian historiography, to appropriate the terms of its discourse. Hence the need for a careful appraisal.

Wink is emphatic in his wholesale rejection of Henri Pirenne. He, however, seems to be a Pirenne himself. Empirically, many of Pirenne's conclusions have been disputed—most notably the negative role of early Arab conquests and raids in the economic life of the Mediterranean—while some others have been supported by the later research, most notably the upsurge in commerce and urbanization from about the eleventh century. However, the most fundamental critique of Pirenne—which runs through both his valid and invalid conclusions—has been of the primacy he assigned to long-distance trade as the prime mover of history.¹ And it is obvious that for Wink, too, long-distance trade is the fulcrum as it were of historical movement.

Wink, however, is but a poor camp-follower of the great Belgian, who was second to none in critical acumen and scholarly depth. To begin with, Wink misrepresents the general character of the critique of Pirenne's thesis that Islam in its early centuries virtually put an end to the long-distance trade of Western Europe. In criticism of Pirenne, historians have pointed not only to the evidence for trade between the Islamic world and Europe, but also to the emergence of new trade routes as the Arabs made commerce difficult on the older routes. Again, there can be no doubt about the hindrances to peaceful trade caused by the Arab invasions of the ninth century; the point against Pirenne is that commerce continued in spite of these raids. Historians still believe in important differences between Merovingian and Carolingian economies, but criticize Pirenne for having overdrawn the contrast.²

Wink goes far ahead of these criticisms and asserts that the *reverse* of what Pirenne said was the case. In his view, Islam led to an all-round promotion of European economy. The dinar was the dominant currency of Europe and Byzantium till the eleventh century. This, together with the Arab accounts, shows the economic hegemony of the Islamic world over Europe and Byzantium (pp. 25, 34-36, 37, 38, 224).

Wink cites an impressive array of authorities in his support (p. 34, fn. 20). I examined three of them—the latest ones—and *they do not support him*. For instance, let us look at the cited pages (pp. 57, 92-115) of F. Braudel's *Civilization and Capitalism: 15th-18th Century*, Vol. III, *The Perspectives of the World*. Page 57 is irrelevant; so are most other pages. The relevant pages speak of the revival of trade in the eighth and ninth centuries after "the crisis provoked by successive waves of Islamic invasion" (*ibid.*, p. 106) and triangular trade between Islam, Byzantium and Western Europe, *with an explicit repudiation of the thesis of Islamic leadership* (*ibid.*, pp. 106-8).

Richard Hodges is the next authority invoked by Wink. His *Dark Age Economics* does refer occasionally to trade with the Arabs from the late eighth century,³ but that is very marginal to

1 See, for example, Rodney Hilton, ed, *The Transition from Feudalism to Capitalism* (New Left Books, 1976); Lewis Mumford, *The City in History* (Pelican, 1979; first published in 1961), p. 293.

2 For a convenient summary, see N.J.G. Pounds, *An Economic History of Medieval Europe* (Longman, London, 1974), pp. 71-75, 78-79.

3 *Dark Age Economics: The Origins of Towns and Trade A.D. 600-1000* (Duckworth, London, 1982), pp. 38, 122, 154, 160.

the narrative. He also has no hesitation in referring to the adverse impact of the Arab trade.⁴ Pirenne argued that the adverse impact of the Muslims on the Mediterranean trade was decisive; Wink believes that it was the positive impact of the Muslims that was decisive; the most recent judgement of the critics (R. Hodges and D. Whitehouse, cited by Wink in his favour) will have none of both: "By removing the critical role of Islam in the Mediterranean in the formation of early medieval Europe we have demolished one of the planks with which Pirenne constructed his historical model".⁵

In fact Wink follows the views of Maurice Lombard first stated in 1947. These do not seem to find favour with the majority of the leading historians.⁶ Hodges and Whitehouse appreciate Lombard's contributions to the Pirenne debate without committing themselves to any such thing as "economic Islamization" of Europe.⁷

A still better idea of Wink's hodgepodge understanding of medieval European historiography can be had from his following remarks on the origin of feudalism:

Europe was gradually drained of its gold due to its unfavourable balance of trade with the Levant and now relied on an indigenous silver currency of very inferior quality. Without gold, its trade with the Byzantine Orient was suspended and Europe was reorganized along feudal lines (pp.33-34).

Pirenne is thus disposed of. The turn of the India trade of the Arabs from the seventh to the eleventh century comes next. We are promised an account of how "it was the India trade which became the *main* external source of wealth for Islam" (p.25, emphasis added). Let us not mind that the promise is not fulfilled and come straight to the "nature of the India trade itself, that is, about the products which went into that trade, their quantities and relative importance, and to what extent a pattern evolved which was typical of the early medieval period as distinct from the classical or late-classical trade" (p.59). It turns out to be a much taller—and about as hollow—promise, for what follows is a bare listing of the export items from India. Here we begin to become familiar with the two features of the book: lack of control over the narrative and absolute liberty with chronology. Slaves take more than half the space in the description of export items from India, with references ranging from "the turn of the seventh" to the seventeenth century, punctuated by constant reminders that slaves were the least significant of all export items (pp. 61-63). For a great many other items, Al-Idrisi (twelfth century) and the works of S.D. Goitein based on the Cairo Geniza papers, the bulk of which becomes important only from the late eleventh century, are cited. L. Gopal's article is cited *in toto* to show the export of "silk, brocade, cotton and jute" from India during this period. Gopal's article no doubt pertains to c. A.D. 700-1100, as indicated in its title, but it talks about the export of textiles only in the last two pages, the items being cotton and buckram and the references being from the twelfth-thirteenth and the fourteenth centuries. A more satisfactory listing is to be found in Maqbul Ahmad's *Indo-Arab Relations*, with an accurate summing up of the limitations of our knowledge:

4 Ibid., pp. 39, 189.

5 *Mohammed, Charlesmagne and the Origins of Europe—Archaeology and the Pirenne Thesis* (Duckworth, London, 1988), p.175.

6 F. Braudel, *op.cit.*, pp. 95-96; N.J.G. Pounds, *op.cit.*, p. 116 and fn. 17.

7 *Op.cit.*, pp. 7-10, 158.

It is difficult to say anything about the general effects of this trade on the economy of the respective countries as the details of the imports and the exports and the periodic trade figures and balances have not yet been worked out.⁸

What Maqbul Ahmad finds “difficult” is but child’s play for Wink, who now sets out to describe the communities of Muslim, Jew and Parsi merchants that carried on this trade. The “largest communities” of Muslim merchants till the tenth century A.D. were on the Gujarat-Konkan coast: “... in the tenth century the Muslim geographers describe a flourishing Arab mercantile culture on the Gujarat-Konkan coast, and these settlements dated back to the ninth, the eighth and in some cases perhaps even to the seventh century” (p. 68). Since the Arab accounts of India do not date from before the mid-ninth century, one would like to have the primary source for the dating of these settlements to as far back as the seventh century. Instead, we are asked to make do with a secondary work, the English translation of which (S. Khuda Bukhsh, *The Orient under the Caliphs*, University of Calcutta, 1920) does not seem to contain the information.⁹

Next we are told about the “considerable migration” of Parsis to India “in the centuries subsequent to the Arab conquest of Persia” (p. 104), “in the eighth century in all probability” (p. 105). This date is based on the *Qiṣṣa-yi-Sanjān* of c.A.D. 1600 by Bahman Kaikobād: “If the dates given in this text are taken at face-value, the landing in Gujarat occurred in 785 A.D.” (p. 107). So what was true “in all probability” becomes taking dates “at face-value”. S.H. Hodivala adduced good reasons why the dates in the account must not be taken at their face value and why we should not date the Parsi immigration before the tenth century. His conclusion is unscrupulously relegated as just “another date”, without discussion, to a footnote (p. 107, fn. 144). In fact, our knowledge of the Parsi activities on the west coast till the end of the tenth century is quite meagre, but see the edifice that is built:

In fact, it seems more than likely that the migration of Parsis to the westcoast (*sic*) of India was not so much a flight as a readjustment of commercial patterns A possible explanation of the rise of more permanent settlement of Parsis on India’s westcoast (*sic*) is that Arab competition in the Persian Gulf forced them to shift the centre of their activities eastward. With the Arabs becoming predominant in the trade of Fars, the Parsis would then have concentrated in the territories of the Cālūkyas, the Hindu dynasty with which Persian diplomatic and trade relations were of long standing (p. 105).

It is not just that this grandiose generalization is baseless. It also contradicts Wink’s earlier statements about the predominance of Arabs on the west coast of India (pp. 65, 68) and forgets that the Rāṣṭrakūṭas had replaced the Cālūkyas on the west coast before A.D. 785.

About the trading settlements of the Jews in India, Wink observes: “The eighth to twelfth centuries, in summary, were the palmy age of the Jews in India, but Jewish success in India was dependent on the presence of the Jews in the Islamic Middle East and Egypt and hence did not

8 Maqbul Ahmad, *Indo-Arab Relations* (New Delhi, 1969), p.86.

9 S. Khuda Bukhsh’s translation does not give full reference to Kramer’s work and simply states : Translated from von Kramer’s, *Culturgeschichte des Orients unter den Chalifen*. It has 463 pages, but one does not know whether he translated both the volumes of the work. Wink cites A. von Kramer, *Culturgeschichte des Orients unter den Chalifen*, 2 vols (Vienna, 1875-77), Vol. II, p.ii

survive the latter's migration to Europe" (p.86). Of these "palmy" days till the late tenth/early eleventh century, we have no definite evidence, as Wink himself *knows*: "The first definite proof of the existence of a Jewish colony near Cranganore is ... the Tamil charter of Bhāskara Ravivarman (978–1036 A.D.) ..." (p. 100). It does not strike Wink that the abundance of evidence of Jews' commercial presence till the eleventh century in other parts of the globe (pp. 86–100) should contrast so starkly with the measly evidence for their presence in India during the same period, and that this in turn should contrast so poorly with conspicuous Jewish presence in India during the twelfth and thirteenth centuries (p. 100).

The arbitrary pushing back of the dates of the various trading communities would support Wink's oft-repeated thesis that there was an all-round expansion of commerce in the Indian Ocean from the seventh/eighth century and that there was an *increase in the volume* of commerce after the Arabs took over from the Persians the role of dominant tradesmen. There is, however, little worthwhile evidence for the commercial contacts of India with the Arabs in the book during the seventh and eighth centuries with the exception of the late eighth century Sind.

Dangerous as such negative evidence is, it would nevertheless support a thesis worthy of our attention that the first century of the rise of Islam saw a decline in the scale of commerce between India and the Arab world. The Arab trade revived only after the founding of Baghdad in A.D. 762, according to this thesis.¹⁰ Even after that, however, there remains a gap of about a hundred years—at least in our knowledge—regarding Indo-Arab trade relations,¹¹ though the mid-ninth century account of merchant Sulaiman does presuppose a certain continuity of this trade from an unspecified previous period. The conclusion that the international trade of the Persian Gulf picked up only after the founding of Baghdad, in fact from the late eighth century, is reached on the basis of detailed archaeological evidence by Hodges and Whitehouse.¹²

The decline in sea-borne commerce between India and the Middle East may also be seen in the information in Wink's book on the history of the port of Debal. An important port during the Gupta/Sassanid period, it was given away as dowry to the Sassanid king Bahram V (p. 48). During the ninth and tenth centuries it was again a flourishing centre of commerce (p. 182). It is thus significant to find during the seventh-early eighth centuries its waters thoroughly infested by pirates: "The Muslim sources insist that it was the persistent insolence of the pirates of Debal and other lairs which forced the Arabs to subjugate the 'frontier of al-Hind'". Piracy may presuppose a certain continuity of sea-borne traffic, but pirates dominating the *port* of Debal, the only important port in Sind, do indicate a fall in its trading fortunes compared to the earlier and the later periods. As Wink himself states, the trade at Debal did not become important till the late eighth century (p. 51, also p. 182).

10 Salih Ahmad El-'Ali, *Al-Tanzimat al-Ijtima'iyā wa'l-Iqtisadiyā fi'l-Basra* (Baghdad, 1953), pp. 232-33, cited in Maqbul Ahmad, *op.cit.*, p.85 (cf.p.81).

11 Much would depend on a more careful and extensive study of Indian literary sources and on the progress of early medieval Indian archaeology. See D. Pingree, "Sanskrit Evidence for the Presence of Arabs, Jews and Persians in Western India: ca 700-1300", *Journal of the Oriental Institute*, Vol. 31, Pt. 2 (Baroda, 1981), pp. 172-82; B.D. Chattopadhyaya, "Markets and Merchants in Early Medieval Rajasthan", *Social Science Probing*, Vol. 2, No.4 (1985), pp. 414-15; P.N. Vasa, "Find of A Late Byzantine Solidus and Arab Ummayyad Dinara from Kutch", *Numismatic Digest*, Vol. 14 (Bombay, 1990), pp.30-33.

12 *Op.cit.*, p. 156.

The relation between trade, coined money and urbanization in early medieval India presents tangles, which, in my opinion, have yet to be resolved. When Romila Thapar pointed out the absence of landgrants in Punjab, R.S. Sharma sought to explain it in terms of the continuing importance of commerce in the region. In his support, he drew attention, *inter alia*, to the continuous series of coins from Punjab.¹³ Yet, according to his own later research,¹⁴ this was a period of urban decline in Punjab. The rich data in the *Urban Decay* in fact call for serious rethinking about the relation between coined money and urbanization. For instance, the book shows the decline of most urban centres by the end of the third century A.D. but speaks of the paucity of coins only after the Gupta period.¹⁵ J.S. Deyell's *Living Without Silver* and Sharma's recent paper have brought the level of discussion to a higher pitch. I fail to see a one-to-one relation between Deyell's monetary history and the processes of the gradual demise of the second urbanization and the third urbanization as described by B.D. Chattopadhyaya. Though a votary of the thesis of Indian feudalism, D.N. Jha has long been uncomfortable about its relation to monetary and urban histories. Valuable work on trade and urbanization has been done by V.K. Jain and R. Champakalakshmi.¹⁶ How does Wink contribute to this literature?

Wink claims to present an integrated account of economy and polity in early medieval India, the conclusions of which I summarized in the beginning. I find it too schematic to discuss without separating the two. For Kashmir he describes an uninterrupted series of copper coins through the early medieval period. From the seventh century, gold and silver coins were minted along with copper coins, but since the late ninth century there were only copper coins with the brief exception of Harṣa's reign. We also note that only a few of Wink's references to evidence for long-distance trade come from the ninth-tenth centuries and the rest from the eleventh-twelfth centuries (pp. 245-49). Wink's explanations for this complex story are *ad hoc*. When gold and silver coins appear, they "reflect ... the growing trade in the early medieval period" (p. 246, emphasis added). When they disappear, "we should not forget that trade and coinage are not necessarily related to each other" (p. 247). In fact, Wink's concern is different. It is exorcising the Pirenian ghost: "There is no positive indication that trade came to a stop or that it diminished on account of the expansion of Islam, or otherwise, either in the seventh or eighth centuries or later" (pp. 246-47).

Describing trade and coinage in Bengal, Wink fails to see that the evidence for indigenous coinage tradition in south-east Bengal (pp.270-72) affects his thesis of the universal dominance of the dinar (pp. 308-9). He continues: "The above tends to show that Bengal up to the end of the Gupta period maintained its most important trade relations with the western regions, but after the expansion of Islam and the rise of world-wide Islamic trading diasporas, the main emphasis was on the south-east" (p.272). The "above" shows nothing of the sort. The statement in all likelihood draws on M.R. Tarafdar's work:

Bengal in the Gupta period had trade relationships with the West, which seem to have been

13 R.S. Sharma, *Indian Feudalism*, 2nd edn (Delhi, 1980), pp. 215-16.

14 *Idem*, *Urban Decay in India, c. 300-c. 1000* (Delhi, 1987), pp. 14-19.

15 *Ibid.*, see especially pp. 191-97, 124-25.

16 These works, together with the long-standing stimulating feudalism debate, are enough to show that the Indian historiography, including R.S. Sharma's works, has been much livelier than Wink would allow.

seriously dislocated with the break-up of the Roman empire and the system of maritime commerce it had built up.

Southeast Bengal had altogether a different story to tell.¹⁷

It is clear that "the West" of Tarafdar becomes the "western regions" of Wink. Wink thus distorts Tarafdar; he also borrows the latter's unfounded impressions: the export of rice, the existence of "numerous Arab trading settlements in the Malay peninsula and the Indonesian Archipelago from the seventh to the eleventh centuries" (p. 274); one of these he himself refutes elsewhere in the book, dating the first proper Arab trading settlement in South-East Asia to not before A.D. 878 (pp. 83-84).

About the non-agrarian economy in the Gurjara-Pratihāra kingdom, he remarks: "Such a dense and variegated urban pattern, it is obvious, leaves little room for a demonetization thesis" (p. 300). In saying so, he is unaware of the lack of fit between the process of urbanization (four urban centres from the late ninth century, the large majority from the eleventh century onwards, pp. 296-300) and the history of coinage (continued prevalence from the seventh century onwards, pp. 300-2). Moreover, towns from the post-Gurjara-Pratihāra period and from outside their domain (for example, Andhra Pradesh) are included in the discussion on "the phenomenal rate of growth of urban centres" based on "the evidence relating to Gurjara-Pratihāra dominions" (p. 297). In a wilful manipulation of B.D. Chattopadhyaya's papers, three townships and one incipient urban centre from the Gurjara-Pratihāra period become "innumerable townships" in Wink's account (p. 298, fn. 234) at the same time as the description of a tenth century Kalacuri town is vivisected into the description of two towns to show a hierarchy of urban centres (p. 298, fn. 232). Alberuni shares Chattopadhyaya's tragic fate; petty miscopyings apart, Wink places Ayodhya, Varanasi, Pataliputra, Munger, Gangasagara, etc., "in the westward direction" of Kanauj on his authority (p. 299, fn. 239)!

The trading relations of the Rāṣṭrakūṭas with the Arabs are stressed in the description of their economy in order to show their supposed political supremacy. Yet Wink does not provide any evidence to show that the Arabs had closer commercial ties with them than with the Pālas. Worse, he not only invokes the tenth-to-twelfth century evidence (Ibn Hauqal, Alberuni and Al-Idrisi) for mercantile centres in Gujarat to argue the case for the economic foundations of Rāṣṭrakūṭa political supremacy from the mid-eighth to the mid-tenth century, but also to demonstrate their political decline from the late tenth century with the waning of this Arab trade (pp. 306-8)!

The schematic end which so often makes Wink obliterate chronological distinctions makes him for once invoke chronology in the case of mercantile economy on the Coromandel coast. Here he describes the upsurge in trade and urbanization from the eleventh century onwards. There is also an interesting critique of the views of G.W. Spencer. The busy commercial traffic, we agree, must have substantially enhanced the revenue base of the Cōḷa state. There is nothing, however, to suggest that the economic and military might of the Cōḷa state was greater than that of any other contemporary state in the subcontinent, which is what is Wink's claim; moreover,

17 M.R. Tarafdar, "Trade and Society in Early Medieval Bengal", *The Indian Historical Review*, Vol. IV, No.2 (January 1978), p.277.

he is guilty here of suppressing the evidence of the comparable upswing in mercantile activities in contemporary Gujarat, for the sake of his schematism.

It remains to examine Wink's ideas on the early medieval Indian polity. His central notion is that of the "hegemony"/"overlordship"/"supremacy"/"paramountcy" of one regional state over all others:

Different Indian dynasties, it appears, rise to supremacy and claim hegemonic and 'imperial' power over the other dynasties in India in the succeeding centuries of the early medieval period. Such supreme power is more than 'ritual sovereignty'; it is much less than centralized imperial control but it is related to relative wealth, and to political and military power, which in each case is derived from strategic alliances or support from or economic-commercial links with the great powers outside the sub-continent (p. 231).

The Kārkoṭa dynasty of Kashmir is named as the first claimant to paramountcy, but the story really begins with the Cāḷukyas of Badami, as do howlers. Harṣavardhana "established Kanauj... as the capital of Āryāvarta ..., thereby challenging the Cāḷukyas who for about 150 years had been paramount kings of India while residing in the Western Deccan" (p. 240). The Cāḷukyas had just completed one hundred years by the end of Harṣa's rule, while the beatings they received from the Pallavas would surely discount the theory of their supremacy even in south India. Harṣa challenged the Cāḷukyas by marching to the Deccan with an army, and not by capturing Kanauj.

The trans-regional political significance of Kanauj seems to have crystallized during and thanks to Harṣa's reign. Wink assigns this significance to Kanauj from before Harṣa's reign: "Having made himself master of Kanauj, Harṣa appears to have been able to legitimate his expansionist ambitions; many North India kings *now* began to acknowledge his paramountcy, ..." (p. 289) (emphasis added). In fact Harṣa began to rule from Kanauj right from the early—if not the first—years of his reign. It was through campaigns—and not control of Kanauj—that he made other kings acknowledge his overlordship. Unmindful of all this, Wink believes that Kanauj in the early medieval period achieved its "focal position" by supplanting Ayodhya which held this position in the ancient period when Kanauj was "second in importance to Ayodhya" (p. 288). That should be news even to the best-informed!

King Lalitāditya Muktāpīḍa of Kashmir is said to have achieved political supremacy by virtue of his *digvijaya* campaign through most of India (pp. 243-44). What made it possible? Wink relates how first Candrāpīḍa and then his successor Lalitāditya requested the Chinese for military help. Each time the help did not come (pp. 242-43). The conclusion: "There is no doubt that Lalitāditya Muktāpīḍa did receive substantial material and military support from the Tang Chinese" (p. 243) which explains the success of Lalitāditya's *digvijaya*.

After Lalitāditya, Dharmapāla of Bengal became for a brief period in the second half of the eighth century "the paramount lord of Northern India" (p.267). The explanation: "A matter of certitude is also the Pāla's alliance with Kashmir and with the Chinese against the Tibetans—and hence indirectly the Arabs—in the eighth century" (p. 266). No evidence again is offered for the alliance with the Chinese, while the Kashmiri alliance is inferred from the fact of Kashmiri invasion (pp. 266-67)—the Kashmir king attacking the Pālas to befriend them with a self-effacing gift of the hegemonic status to boot!

Then come the Rāṣṭrakūṭas: "At the time that the Gurjara-Pratihāras exercised hegemony in North India, the *Ballaharā* king became paramount overlord of India as a whole. Such

paramountcy, it appears from Sanskrit and Arabic sources alike, the dynasty retained for about two hundred years, until the late tenth century ..." (p. 303). It is only by a most credulous acceptance of the Arab geographers' accounts that one may support Wink's notion of the all-India paramountcy of the Rāṣṭrakūṭas. The Sanskrit sources do not support any such thing—Wink's claim is certainly false. He also equates the nature of Gurjara-Pratihāra overlordship with that of the Rāṣṭrakūṭa one: this exposes the vacuity of his notion of "paramountcy", etc., at one stroke, for the Sanskrit sources describe the nature of Gurjara-Pratihāra (and Rāṣṭrakūṭa) overlordship in a way that is utterly different from Wink's accounts of the Pāla or Rāṣṭrakūṭa or other "overlordships". Reading just the Ujjain Inscription of Mahendrapāla II or the Hansot Grant of Bhartṛvaddha will bring the point home to him.¹⁸

During the eleventh century, we are told next, the Cōḷa state was "no doubt" "the most powerful Indian state" (pp.314-15). All that can be said in its support is a successful raid into the small kingdoms of Bengal. In fact, the internecine wars between the Cōḷas and the Cāḷukyas of Kalyāṇa show the former's inability to impose their overlordship over the neighbouring kingdom, much less the other such states of the time (Caulukyās of Gujarat, Paramāras of Malwa, etc.). Rājārāja I carried a raid successfully into the Cāḷukya kingdom,¹⁹ but a few years later, in the beginning of the eleventh century, Rājendra I had to form a confederacy with two other powers—Paramāras and Kalacuris—for a second invasion. The Cāḷukya Jayasimha II, however, was able to repulse them all.²⁰ The Cōḷas' fight with the Cāḷukyas continued through the eleventh century. They did score successes, but were driven out each time, and on more than one occasion suffered ignominies also such as when Someśvara I and Vikramāditya VI occupied Kāñci.²¹

Such internecine wars ought to suggest—as Romila Thapar pointed out in an earlier context²²—that the strength of the contending states was about evenly balanced. Singling out a raid or two for establishing a state's "paramountcy", if pursued seriously, would boggle Wink's mind in ways he cannot imagine!

I reached the end of my tether with the examination of Wink's exposition of the following: (i) the location of Malwa; (ii) state formation in Vengi; (iii) distribution of Cāhamāna lineages; and (iv) history of *agni-kula* myth. Wink does not seem to be sure where Malwa is. At one place, he distinguishes Avanti from Malwa (placing it "towards" Malwa, p. 280), and at another place he places Malwa in the Deccan (p. 303). He even seems to think that Malwa was to the north of Chanderi (p. 285). About Vengi, Wink states: "Here it was not before the middle of the twelfth century that agricultural settlements had proceeded far enough for a settled state to emerge for the first time" (p. 315). Ever heard of the Viṣṇukuṇḍins, the Iksvākus or the Eastern Cāḷukyas?

Wink forgets sober history while analysing the fire-pit (*agni-kunḍa*) myth of the origin of the Rajputs. According to him, it was with this myth that the Pratihāras, the Paramāras, the

18: *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. XIV, pp. 160-61; *ibid.*, Vol. XII, pp. 197-204.

19 D.C. Ganguly, "Later Chalukyas and Kalachuris of Kalyana" in *History and Culture of the Indian People*, Vol. V, *The Struggle for Empire*, 2nd edn (Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Bombay, 1966), pp. 164-65.

20 *Ibid.*, p. 166.

21 *Ibid.*, pp. 167-71, 173-75, 177-79. K.A. Nilakanta Sastri, "The Cāḷukyas of Kalyana" in R.S. Sharma and K.M. Shrivastava, ed., *A Comprehensive History of India*, Vol. IV, Pt I (A.D. 985-1206) (People's Publishing House, New Delhi, 1922), pp. 80-81, 90.

22 *A History of India*, Vol. I (Pelican, 1966), p. 173.

Caulukyās and the Cāhamānas sought to “cover up” their “obscure, (semi-) nomadic, aboriginal but also partly foreign origin” in early medieval India (pp. 285, 291) : “the ceremony was doubtlessly meant to enhance the social respectability of such clans as had *thus far* remained beyond the pale of Hindu civilization” (p. 291, emphasis added). The fact is that in the early medieval period only the Paramāras claimed descent from the fire-pit. The Cāhamānas and the Caulukyās themselves did not associate themselves with the myth, although they knew it well and claimed other forms of supernatural descent.²³ The story as recounted by Tod is based on the work by Chand Bardai; even there it was inserted by some later interpolator, the earliest manuscripts having an altogether different origin myth of the Cāhamānas;²⁴ as late as the fourteenth century the literary works in the Cāhamāna court refer to a different origin of the Cāhamānas than the fire-pit one.²⁵ The Pratihāras, the Caulukyās and the Cāhamānas won their place within “the pale of Hindu civilization” entirely without the *agni-kula* myth.

The historical significance of the *agni-kula* myth as argued by Wink is thus untenable. So is his description of the myth: “... great disorder prevailed due to the absence of the strong arm. The kṣatriyās of Hind were created through the expiatory rites of the sages and the gods. At the same convocation ... the new warriors were incited to defend the brāhmaṇical religion against the *mleccha* Muslims” (p. 292). The *agni-kunḍa* ritual was not expiatory; nor were the warriors created to fight Muslims. Some descriptions, including the one recorded by Abul Fazl, do have the Rajputs created to fight the Buddhists,²⁶ but never the Muslims. The *Prthvīrājavijaya* of Jayānaka states that the Cāhamānas were produced to wipe out the *mlecchas*, but it gives their origin from the sun²⁷ and not from the *agni-kunḍa*.

Wink claims elsewhere (p.286, fn.193) to have read the pages from Ray’s *Dynastic History* which I cited to question his views on the *agni-kula* myth. There he cites from about a hundred pages from the book to support his following account of the history of the Cāhamānas:

...the Cāhamānas originally belonged to the Sambhar region, whence they moved into the Ganges-Yamuna valley, where they became divided in many branches, the rulers of which were subordinate to the Gurjara-Pratihāras. Throughout the period 750-950 A.D., at least, most of the Cāhamāna domains were incorporated in the Pratihāra polity. In the tenth century they succeeded in establishing themselves as overlords of Rajasthan and in parts of the Punjab and Gujarat (pp.285-86).

What Ray actually describes, with enviable clarity, is this: the Cāhamānas of Sambhar extended their domains (and not “moved into”) to include Punjab and the Yamuna valley, in the twelfth century when the Gurjara-Pratihāras were a thing of the past. The four ruling lineages of the Cāhamānas which branched off from the Sambhar Cāhamānas were located in southern Rajasthan (those of Naḍḍula, Jāvalipura, Raṇasthambhapura and Satyapura), and were never

23 H.C. Ray, *The Dynastic History of Northern India : Early Medieval Period*, 2nd edn (Delhi, 1973), Vol. II, pp.1052-53; A.K. Majumdar, *Caulukyās of Gujarat* (Bombay, 1956), pp. 8-9; P. Bhatia, *The Paramaras* (Delhi, 1970), pp. 8-9.

24 A.K. Majumdar, op.cit., p.9

25 H.C. Ray, op.cit., p. 1053 and fn. 1.

26 P. Bhatia, op.cit., p. 10, fn.5.

27 Dasharatha Sharma, *Early Chauhan Dynasties*, 2nd edn (Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, 1975), pp. 5,7.

subordinate to the Gurjara-Pratihāras. During A.D. 750-950, we see four Cāhamāna lineages (those of Sambhar, Dhavalapurī and Partabgarh in Rajasthan, and of Lāṭa in Gujarat) as subordinate to the Gurjara-Pratihāras at varying points of time. In the tenth century the Cāhamānas laid no claim to the overlordship of Rajasthan, and are not heard of at all in Gujarat and Punjab. Finally, although Ray calls the Sambhar region “possibly the cradle-land of the tribe” (op.cit, p.1054), this seems doubtful in the absence of any known relation between the Cāhamānas of Sambhar and those of Lāṭa, Dhavalapurī and Partabgarh, and to be disproved by the possibly earlier emergence of the Cāhamānas of Lāṭa than those of Sambhar, all on Ray’s own showing.

So how did Wink perform this impossible caricature? One does not have to go far; all he has done is to misread the first four pages of the cited ones (Ray, op.cit., pp.1052-55).

I should like to close with a clarification. It must not be thought that I examined a wider range of references to give a selected account of the faulty ones. I had to select nothing; the paper represents about the sum total of the energy I spent on the book; I gave up only after getting convinced that I could not depend even for isolated pieces of information on this gift from such famed publishers.